

Role of Anti-corruption commission in curbing corruption in Bangladesh

How effective is Bangladesh's
anti-corruption campaign in
combating corruption?

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INTRODUCTION

Corruption is the misappropriation of power for personal benefit. Corruption undermines confidence, undermines democracy, stifles economic development, and exacerbates inequality, poverty, social division, and the environmental disaster. Politicians, government officials, public servants, business persons, and members of the public can all be involved in corruption. Corruption can occur in a variety of settings, including business, government, the courts, the media, and civil society, as well as in a variety of sectors ranging from health and education to infrastructure and sports.

To combat corruption, the government established an Anti-Corruption Commission. The ACC is the state's statutory independent corruption prevention and detection body. Previously, the Bureau of Anti-Corruption (BAC), established in 1957 by the Anti-Corruption Act of 1957, was responsible for anti-corruption efforts (ACC Annual Report, 2018, p12).

However, because the BAC lacked the authority to independently investigate and investigate charges of corruption, it was unable to satisfy the expectation of effectively combating corruption. When the present ACC was founded on November 21, 2004, under the Anti-Corruption Commission Act 2004, the BAC was abolished (ACC Annual Report, 2018, p13).

This article seeks to respond to the following question, "Discuss the role of Anti-corruption commission in curbing corruption by drawing inferences from some recent corruption cases. How effective do you think the anti-corruption is in curbing corruption in Bangladesh?". The Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) is believed to be attempting to combat corruption by citing recent examples. It will also claim that the Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) is less effective in Bangladesh in combating corruption, and that the ACC can be made more effective by taking certain steps.

ROLE OF ACC IN CURBING CORRUPTION

The ACC's vision is "to ensure creating a strong anti-corruption culture that permeates throughout the whole society", and its mission is "to combat, control, prevent corruption relentlessly and promote good practices" (ACC website, 2021).

The ACC's strategic objectives are to curb corruption through ways of punitive actions; to prevent corruption in revising the existing work procedures; and to prevent corruption through education, burgeoning good practices, and disseminating awareness (ACC website, 2021).

To prevent corruption and the misdeeds associated with corruption in compliance with the Anti-Corruption Commission Act 2004, the responsibilities are to conduct inquiries, investigate corruption and other specified offenses, and discharge duties as a prosecuting agency (ACC Annual Report, 2018, p13).

The ACC has recently filed the following cases in order to combat corruption:

A case has been launched against PK Haldar by the Anti-Corruption Commission. On January 8, 2020, for allegedly accumulating Tk275 crore in unlawful assets. PK Haldar, former managing director (MD) of NRB Global Bank and International Leasing and Financial Services Limited (ILFSL). The Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) has identified 62 people linked to Prashant Kumar Haldar's alleged money laundering. The names of 62 people have been discovered by the ACC investigating officer in connection with the alleged misappropriation of thousands of crores of taka. These 62 people have been fined Tk1,057.80 crore by the ACC (The Business Standard, 2021).

Hundreds of documents on plots, flats, and houses were confiscated by the Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) from Prashant Kumar (PK) Halder's underground warehouse. Initially, 7,060 decimals of land have been identified, with a value of at least Tk1,000 crore. Aside from this case, another team of the commission is investigating Halder's fraud case. The ACC filed five cases against 31 people, including Halder, in the first phase of the International Leasing fraud case on January 25, after a lengthy investigation. Secret sources have told the ACC that PK Halder had transported thousands of crores of rupees to Singapore, India, and Canada.

Halder did not return, despite the court's permission, and an Interpol arrest order was filed against him (The Business Standard, 2021).

On November 12, 2020, the ACC filed a complaint against Samrat, stating that he amassed an illicit wealth of Tk2.94 crore. The ACC took the latest step against money laundering as part of its investigation into the matter, after discovering documented evidence against Samrat. The Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) stated that Ismail Chowdhury Samrat, the expelled head of the Jubo League, laundered more than Tk219 crore in Singapore and Malaysia despite having no major assets in the nation. According to the ACC, between 2011 and 2019, Samrat laundered 3.65 million Singapore dollars, or Tk219 crore, in Singapore. The funds were placed in two casinos, one of which was Marina Bay Sands, Singapore's most opulent. Meanwhile, in April of 2014, Samrat conducted a transaction worth 2.05 lakh Malaysian ringgits (about Tk48.58 lakh) at a Malaysian casino. The ACC inquiry found that the ejected governing party's youth wing head illegally amassed more than Tk223 crore, of which more than Tk219 crore was laundered, transformed, and smuggled out of the country. As a result, the commission decided to file a money laundering charge sheet with the court (The Business Standard, 2020).

On August 2020, the Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) filed a charge against Shamima Nur Papia, the suspended leader of the Jubo Mohila League, and her husband Mofizur Rahman Sumon for fraudulently collecting Tk 6.24 crore. Papia paid Tk 3.23 crore in cash to the Westin hotel between October 12, 2019 and February 22, 2020, according to the court statement (The Daily Star, 2020).

The charge sheet against Papia and her husband Mofizur Rahman in a case claiming unlawful asset acquisition has been accepted by the Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC). The case's investigating officer completed the investigation and filed the report. Papia and her husband Moti Sumon, according to the report, have illegally earned Tk5,84,18,718 through mutual connivance (The Business Standard, 2021).

On February 20, 2021, the Anti-Corruption Commission (ACC) filed two complaints against Abdul Malek, a former driver at the Directorate General of Health Services, and his wife for amassing wealth from sources other than known sources of income.

According to the first case statement, driver Malek gave the anti-graft agency a false and baseless asset statement by concealing information about movable and immovable assets worth more than Tk93 lakh. He also had more than Tk1.5 crore in moveable and immovable wealth, which did not match his known sources of income. Driver Malek and his wife Nargis Begum were also charged in the second instance. On mutual conciliation, the two was sued for retaining wealth worth roughly Tk1.10 crore, which was gained unlawfully, in the custody of Nargis Begum, according to the case statement (The Business Standard, 2021).

After probing charges of unlawful wealth acquisition, ACC filed a case against DIG Mizan at the Integrated District Office (Dhaka-1) on June 24, 2019. DIG Mizan and his nephew Sub-Inspector Mahmudul Hasan are both in custody in this case. The ACC discovered that he gained wealth worth TK 3.28 crore while concealing riches worth TK 3.7 crore in his wealth statement, according to the case statement (United news of Bangladesh, 2020).

ACC IS INEFFECTIVE IN CURBING CORRUPTION

The Anti-Corruption Commission was established by a legislation passed on February 23, 2004; however, it has generally been ineffective in terms of proactive investigations aimed at preventing corruption. Because of abuses of governance, the ACC is ineffectual; some parts of our law enforcement organizations benefit from corruption, political favoritism, and a culture of impunity (Dhaka Tribune, 2018).

It is widely acknowledged that once corruption has established itself, it is exceedingly difficult to prevent it from spreading, which is why it is imperative to confront corruption as soon as possible. In Bangladesh, however, it appears that the ACC is only allowed to examine corruption by government higher-ups. The ACC promised at the outset of the year that it would uncover and punish individuals responsible for the gambling industry accountable. During the early stages of the anti-casino campaign, a few notable names emerged, including some ruling party MPs. However, with the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic and subsequent investigations into health-care abuses, the anti-casino campaign has faded (The Dailly Star, 2020).

As a result, cases involving significant criminal offenses like as extortion, homicide, abduction, and forcible takeover of property can sometimes go unsolved, resulting in widespread human rights violations (Dhaka Tribune, 2018).

In 2016, the ACC investigated 1,007 complaints out of 12,990 in Bangladesh, indicating that it is unsuccessful in combating corruption. In 2019, 1,710 complaints were investigated out of a total of 21,371 (Bdnews24, 2020).

The Anti-Corruption Commission Act of 2004 renders the ACC impotent. The ACC Act of 2004 has a number of flaws, but it does make the Commission subject to government financial and administrative oversight in any case. According to Section 25 (1) The Government allocate the amount of money fixed in favor of the Commission for expenditure for every financial year. (ACC Act 2004). That means the Commission is not fully free to use its budget independently.

According to Article 23 (1) The Commission may, at the time of inquiry or investigation into allegations of corruption, within a time specified by it, call for any report or information from the Government or any authority or organization under the Government or may seek expertise assistance of one or more officer, who are skilled, experienced and expert in relevant issues, and in case of failure of receiving the report or information called for within the specified time, the Commission may on its own motion enquire into or investigate the concerned complaints (ACC Act 2004). That means the authority of the Government is not bound to provide information.

The administrative authority of the Commission is also restricted. According to Article 30 clearly states that the Commission's organizational structure and budget will be determined by the Government (ACC Act 2004). That means the Commission is not free to form its organizational structure.

The ACC's independence and neutrality are founded on its operations and use of power. Many experts believe that ACC is used to harass opposition politicians, but that it is liberal when it comes to politicians from the ruling party/alliance. All of this indicates that ACC is not politically neutral; its activities are politically biased and not consistent across the board. Its functional independence is further hampered by pressure from the government, the ruling party, and other parties. Furthermore, according to the Public Service Act 2018, pursuing complaints against government personnel requires prior consent from the government.

During 2016-18, the ACC budget remained at 0.031 percent of the national budget, despite the fact that the international standard for such a budget was 0.2 percent. The training budget has also remained unchanged at 0.5 percent, despite the fact that the international standard is 1.3 percent.

Furthermore, the ACC lacks experience in cases involving unlawful property transfers, banking misconduct, asset embezzlement, and so like. The caliber of panel lawyers hired in the districts is lacking. The lack of a thorough method to watch and review ACC's activities, as well as the fact that it only submits an annual report to the president, are the main sources of worry. Even in parliament, there is no discussion of this report. Despite the fact that the commission has a supervision and evaluation department for evaluating inquiry findings, there is no provision in this framework for people's representation. There are no specific conduct guidelines for the commission's workers. ACC investigated only 6.75 percent of complaints in the detection, investigation, and prosecution dimension from 2016 to 2018, despite the fact that the international benchmark in this area is above 66 percent. Only 21% of the investigations were converted into cases, despite the fact that the international standard is over 75%. The public's impression of the ACC's neutrality in pursuing cases is negative, indicating a lack of trust in the body. Furthermore, the commission has had no evident progress in discovering high-level corruption. Concerns have also been raised concerning ACC's investigative skills and professionalism. Officials participating in the process have even been accused of bribery and carelessness (The Financial Express, 2020).

HOW ACC CAN BE EFFECTIVE IN CURBING CORRUPTION

Combating corruption is a long-term and multi-faceted task. Having an ACC is not a goal in and of itself; it simply provides an opportunity as part of a larger system. The ACC cannot be a successful organization without the cooperation of key accountability institutions in the national integrity system (NIS), such as an effective Parliament, administration, law enforcement agencies, court, public service, and the office of the comptroller and auditor general. Despite being founded by the government, the ACC must be viewed as an institution that holds the government accountable in the public interest, rather than as a part of it. Combating corruption is a long-term and multi-faceted task. Having an ACC is not a goal in and of itself; it simply provides an opportunity as part of a larger system.

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There are four mutually reinforcing drivers that are required:

The first is political will at all levels, not just on paper but in practice, to allow ACC to carry out its legal and institutional mandate without interference from politics or bureaucracy. Second, the ACC must rediscover itself, particularly in light of the fact that, in addition to its legal authority and institutional capability, it has the prime minister's vow of zero tolerance for corruption on its side. It must relentlessly confront impunity and bring the corrupt to justice, ensuring that all people are treated equally before the law, regardless of their identity or status. Third, both individually and together, the NIS institutions that support the ACC must be transparent, efficient, responsible, and effective. Fourth, a favorable climate must be provided for the general public, notably the media, civil society, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), to generate and increase demand for an effective ACC (The Daily Star, 2019).

The ACC must be provided full independence, which necessitates a review of Article 30 of the Anti-Corruption Act of 2004. The Commission must have the authority to create its own organizational structure, hire its own staff at all levels, and set its own budget, which must be funded by the government. The Act should be changed to allow for the provision of the ACC budget as a Charged Expenditure. Section 25 of the ACC Act 2004 has to be revised to provide the Commission full authority to manage its budget without intervention from the government.

A statutory audit should be used to ensure the ACC's financial responsibility. The Commission must appoint the Secretary of the Commission, not the Government, and the Secretary's rank cannot be increased, nor can the Secretary be granted the title of Chief Accounts Officer. Instead, in addition to the statutory audit, the ACC should establish a strong internal audit unit with trained specialists reporting directly to the Chairman.

The idea to hold the Commission responsible to the President falls short of the goal of accountability. Instead, the ACC should be answerable to a Supreme Court Judicial Committee. Alternatively, the ACC might be accountable to a Parliamentary Committee made up of one representative from each of the Parliament's parties, as long as those members are known for their high levels of trustworthiness, integrity, and honesty.

A Persons Advisory Committee made up of non-partisan prominent citizens with high integrity, honesty, and reliability could be established by law to advise and review the ACC's work. Citizens' Subcommittees can be formed to advise the ACC on specific preventative issues such as education, awareness, and civic involvement.

All ACC workers are required to proactively disclose and update their assets and liabilities statements via the company's website and other means of communication. Because the majority of the ACC's staff hails from the Bureau of Anti-heyday, Corruption's provisions must be implemented to examine the ACC's staff's credibility at all levels through independent inspection. Specific trainings for ACC staff capacity building and professional excellence must be offered, and must be undertaken based on a need's assessment.

The ACC staff's salary and benefits must be proportionate with the cost of living as well as the hazards they face. To impose zero tolerance against corruption, strong negative incentives must be paired with strong positive incentives. To promote effective management, internal self-regulation, and checks and balances, the ACC must create its own Code of Ethics for its employees as well as a Governance Manual.

ACC needs to design a policy so that it can efficiently deploy its resources and capability to handle the massive number of pending cases as well as new ones. Without fear or favor, the political will must be maintained and enforced. Political support and backing must come from all sides of the political aisle (TIB, 2010).

CONCLUSION

Whether we like it or not, Bangladesh routinely finds itself among the list of the most corrupt countries of the world. If the government is really interested in curbing corruption, it has to empower the ACC and other concerned authorities to the point where they are no longer fearful to go after the masterminds behind all these corrupt initiatives. If need be, they must also be equipped with adequate manpower and whatever else is required. Otherwise, no matter how many cosmetic drives and investigations are conducted, corruption will continue to be the biggest impediment to Bangladesh's progress and its prosperity.

REFERENCES

- ✓ ACC Annual Report 2018, p12.
See-
http://acc.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/acc.portal.gov.bd/annual_reports/920837bf_160d_4734_9026_5d0bd0b43b58/acc-annual-report-2018-eng.pdf (last accessed on 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ ACC Annual Report 2018, p13.
See-
http://acc.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/acc.portal.gov.bd/annual_reports/920837bf_160d_4734_9026_5d0bd0b43b58/acc-annual-report-2018-eng.pdf (last accessed 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ ACC website, 2021.
See- <http://acc.org.bd/site/page/957ced4f-ea9e-446e-b1ca-8e7a59c4f374/> (last accessed on 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ ACC website, 2021.
See- <http://acc.org.bd/site/page/957ced4f-ea9e-446e-b1ca-8e7a59c4f374/> (last accessed on 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ ACC, Annual Report 2018, p13.
See-
http://acc.portal.gov.bd/sites/default/files/files/acc.portal.gov.bd/annual_reports/920837bf_160d_4734_9026_5d0bd0b43b58/acc-annual-report-2018-eng.pdf (last accessed 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Business Standard, 2021.
See- <https://tbsnews.net/bangladesh/crime/acc-finds-62-allies-pk-haldar-185932> (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Business Standard, 2021.
See-
<https://tbsnews.net/bangladesh/crime/pk-halders-7060-decimal-land-land-records-confiscated-207481> (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Business Standard, 2020.
See-
<https://tbsnews.net/bangladesh/acc-approves-charge-sheet-against-samrat-over-money-laundering-158257> (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Daily Star, 2020.
See-
<https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.thedailystar.net/city/news/acc-files-case-against-papia-1940001%3famp> (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Business Standard, 2021.
See-
<https://tbsnews.net/bangladesh/crime/acc-approves-charge-sheet-against-papia-200329> (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Business Standard, 2021.
See-
<https://tbsnews.net/bangladesh/corruption/acc-sues-ex-dghs-driver-malek-his-wife-amassing-wealth-illegally-202066> (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ United news of Bangladesh, 2020.
See-
<https://unb.com.bd/m/category/bangladesh/acc-press-charges-against-suspended-dig-mizan-acc-director-basir/41722> (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)

- ✓ Dhaka Tribune, 2018.
See-
<https://www.dhakatribune.com/opinion/op-ed/2018/05/18/the-corruption-dynamics-in-bangladesh> (last accessed on 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ Dhaka Tribune, 2018.
See-
<https://www.dhakatribune.com/opinion/op-ed/2018/05/18/the-corruption-dynamics-in-bangladesh> (last accessed on 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Dailly Star, 2020.
See-
<https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.thedailystar.net/editorial/news/acc-full-sound-and-fury-2008909%3famp> (last accessed on 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ Dhaka Tribune, 2018.
See-
<https://www.dhakatribune.com/opinion/op-ed/2018/05/18/the-corruption-dynamics-in-bangladesh> (last accessed on 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ Bdnews24, 2020.
See- <https://www.google.com/amp/s/m.bdnews24.com/amp/en/detail/bangladesh/1825083> (last accessed on 25 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ ACC Act 2004.
See-
https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.dpp.gov.bd/upload_file/gazettes/24867_42481.pdf&ved=2ahUKewjxltWzv4fvAhVBU30KHdXwDLIQFjABegQIAhAG&usg=AOvVaw3ABfJHXBpxbiZIezKih9Vg (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ ACC Act 2004.
See-
https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.dpp.gov.bd/upload_file/gazettes/24867_42481.pdf&ved=2ahUKewjxltWzv4fvAhVBU30KHdXwDLIQFjABegQIAhAG&usg=AOvVaw3ABfJHXBpxbiZIezKih9Vg (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ ACC Act 2004.
See-
https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://www.dpp.gov.bd/upload_file/gazettes/24867_42481.pdf&ved=2ahUKewjxltWzv4fvAhVBU30KHdXwDLIQFjABegQIAhAG&usg=AOvVaw3ABfJHXBpxbiZIezKih9Vg (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Financial Express, 2020.
See-
<https://thefinancialexpress.com.bd/views/reviews/improving-performance-of-acc-1583420889>
(last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ The Dailly Star, 2019
See-
<https://www.thedailystar.net/supplements/strong-institution-good-governance/news/anti-corruption-commission-how-can-it-be-truly-effective-1701922> (last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)
- ✓ Transparency International Bangladesh, 2010.
See- https://www.ti-bangladesh.org/beta3/images/max_file/pb_ACC_10_en.pdf
(last accessed on 26 Feb, 2021)